

COMPOSITES IN SPACE — CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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ABSTRACT

A review of the growth of polymer matrix composites (PMC) in aerospace applications is presented together with an overview of the space environment. Three aspects of this environment are addressed in detail in terms of their effects on PMC materials — vacuum outgassing, atomic oxygen erosion and impact damage due to micrometeoroids and debris. Ground-based tests and space flight results are presented together with design models for analyzing and predicting these effects on PMC's. The challenges of using PMC's in space are clearly identified and the opportunities for overcoming them presented.

INTRODUCTION

The introduction of polymer matrix composites (PMC's) for aerospace structures began as early as 1940, with the application of glass/polyester to fabricate aircraft radomes [1]. It was not until 1969 that carbon/epoxy materials were applied to operational fighter aircraft structures, quickly followed by their limited use on spacecraft in 1971-72. Other commonly used PMC's such as aramid (Kevlar®)/epoxy (1971), carbon/polyimide (1974), and most recently carbon/thermoplastic (1988) systems followed [1].

Figure 1 shows the progression in the introduction of various PMC's to aircraft and spacecraft.

Figure 1. Evolution of polymer matrix composite applications in aerospace structures [1].

The growth in PMC % structural weight for various types of aircraft is depicted in Figure 2 [2]. It is evident that the largest structural weight fraction appears in fighter aircraft (25 ~ 35%), with transport aircraft ranging from 15 ~ 20%.

Table 1 summarizes the major PMC space structures and fabrication materials that have been developed and flown over the past 25 years. From a Canadian perspective, it is of interest to note that Canada was the third nation to have its own satellite in space (Alouette 1, 1962), and the first to employ a large PMC structure (a graphite/epoxy antenna) on its Anik B spacecraft in 1972 [3]. As more of these PMC's are used in spacecraft structures and components, reliability in terms of their performance and operational lifetime becomes critical. The well-recognized advantages of using PMC's can be mitigated by the effects of a hostile space environment. For example, such properties are high specific stiffness and strength and low coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) can be seriously affected by thermal cycling fatigue cracks, mass loss due to erosion by atomic oxygen (AO), distortion due to vacuum outgassing, radiation damage to the polymer structure and fracture arising from hypervelocity impacts of micrometeoroids and space debris.

The first part of this paper describes the space environment factors that can affect the design and selection of PMC materials for spacecraft applications. Recent results obtained by the author and his colleagues from ground-based testing and space flight experiments are then presented as they relate to three aspects of the space environment — vacuum outgassing, atomic oxygen erosion and hypervelocity particle impacts. In all three cases, guidelines are given that permit estimates of the magnitude of these effects on the material system of interest.

SPACE ENVIRONMENT CHALLENGES

The space environment is characterized by very low pressure (vacuum), temperature extremes depending on the orientation of the material relative to the sun, various atomic species and charged particles in concentrations dependent on altitude and solar activity, electromagnetic radiation, micrometeoroids and space debris. To some extent, all of these factors influence the design of the satellite. Figure 3 characterizes the variation in pressure and temperature with altitude. Large temperature variations can occur due to sunspot activity. However, even using the average atmospheric temperature model, several hundred degree differences can occur between the sun-facing and shadow-facing sides of a spacecraft. The vacuum state surrounding the spacecraft leads to material outgassing which can be quite significant for polymer materials, compared to metallics which pose no concern. Outgassing products consist of trapped volatiles such as water moisture, catalysts and monomer for example.

Figure 2. Growth in use of polymer matrix composites in aircraft structures. (L. F. Vosteen, R. N. Haddock, NASA CR 4620, Nov. 1994)

Table 1. Examples of Spacecraft Applications of Composite Materials

Application	Materials	Satellites/Space Vehicles
Antenna, reflectors, horns, platforms	graphite/epoxy and aramid/epoxy	Anik B - first use of GRE in Space (1972)
Synthetic aperture radar antennas	graphite/epoxy	ERS-1
Antenna feeds, waveguides and microwave filters	graphite/epoxy	Intelsat V
Central tube cylinder	graphite/epoxy sandwich	NAVSTAR GPS GOES Weather Satellites
Solar arrays (telescopic cylindrical arrays)	graphite/epoxy tubes and skins	TDF-1
Tubular truss structures and towers	graphite/epoxy	SPAS, Eureka
Payload bay doors	graphite/epoxy sandwich	Space Shuttle
pressure vessels	aramid/epoxy	Space Shuttle
thermal protection tiles	carbon/carbon	Space Shuttle
Launch vehicle structures	graphite/epoxy	Ariane
Optical structures	graphite/epoxy	Hubble Telescope
Space robot systems	graphite and aramid/epoxy sandwich graphite/Peek	Canadarm Space Shuttle Mobile Service Facility/Space Station

Figure 3. Temperature and pressure profiles as a function of altitude.

Figure 4 presents the concentration of some gaseous species and charged particles as a function of altitude. Two regions are of interest — the low Earth orbit (LEO) regime where most satellites and the space shuttle orbit (including the International Space Station Alpha (ISSA) scheduled for 1997-98) and geosynchronous orbit (GEO). Note that in the latter case, charged particles populate the higher altitudes ($>10^3$ km) while various gaseous species predominate in LEO. Again, the effect of solar activity is significant on the concentration levels. When one examines the altitude profiles of the various gaseous species in more detail (Figure 5), it is evident that atomic oxygen (AO) has the highest number density (i.e., concentration). The fact that it is highly reactive with many forms of carbon (but not diamond) and organic polymers presents a serious challenge in using PMC's in space. Even though the concentration of AO may be low, the actual flux of AO on an orbiting spacecraft travelling at ~ 8 km/s is very high. From Figure 6 one can see that for typical LEO altitudes, the flux can be as high as $\sim 10^{15}$ atoms/cm²-s. Although the AO concentration drops dramatically at higher altitudes, the enormous effect of solar activity can still drive these flux values to $>10^{13}$ atoms/cm²-s.

Figure 4

Figure 5. Low Earth orbital environment.

Figure 6

One other factor that needs to be considered is vacuum ultraviolet radiation (VUV), corresponding to the 100 ~ 200 nm wavelength region. Not only does VUV cause the dissociation of O₂ into atomic oxygen, but it can also react with many polymer materials to alter their properties, and in some instances, break molecular bonds and result in enhanced erosion from AO. Figure 7 presents a schematic of this effect and illustrates how AO can cause erosion of some materials, or the development of passivating oxides when it reacts with Al or Si for example. The energy absorbed by molecules within a polymer is given by the relation

$$E = \frac{2.86 \times 10^5}{\lambda} \text{ (kcal/mole)} \quad (1)$$

where λ is the radiation wavelength. It can be shown that for short wavelength VUV radiation, sufficient energy exists to break many bonds found in polymer materials.

Figure 7. Reaction of atomic oxygen and UV radiation with satellite surface.

The natural micrometeoroid environment poses another major hazard to spacecraft. These microparticles impact at velocities ranging from 8 ~ 70 km/s. A plot of their incident flux values as a function of particle size is given in Figure 8 where it can be seen that little variation in their

distribution occurs over the altitude range of $10^2 \sim 10^3$ km. In addition, orbital debris is also found in this same region with flux values that do vary considerably with altitude. Energies associated with these hypervelocity microparticles are sufficiently high that complete penetration of metallic and composite structures has been observed. However, at this point in time, very little has been published on the associated damage to PMC structures.

Figure 8. Microparticle flux in Earth vicinity.

VACUUM OUTGASSING

In 1984 NASA launched a 9.7 tonne gravity gradient stabilized satellite known as the Long Duration Exposure Facility (LDEF). It had a 12-sided polygon cross-section which provided 86 experiment trays, many of which contained a number of PMC materials. A schematic of LDEF is shown in Figure 9. LDEF was retrieved in 1990 after 5.75 years in orbit. UTIAS had a PMC experiment located at station 12, 82° off the 'ram' direction (i.e., the velocity vector). Many of the UTIAS samples were instrumented with strain and temperature gauges, with measurements taken every 16 hours after launch over a period of 400 days, and stored on a magnetic tape cassette data acquisition system. Figure 10 presents the thermal-strain response of a 5208/T300 graphite/epoxy, 4-ply (90°) tube. It is apparent that about 1600 μ strain distortion occurred after 80 days in the vacuum environment. Much of this 'strain' was recovered when the tube was exposed to the 'ambient' laboratory environment due to re-absorption of water moisture (see Figure 10). The actual change in strain as a function of time in orbit is plotted in Figure 11. Again one can see that the distortion due to outgassing effectively ceases after the 80-day period. The local periods of inactivity (i.e., no monotonic strain change with time) are associated with the inclination of the UTIAS tray (and samples) away from the sun, in which case the shadowing effect caused the sample temperatures to drop below the freezing value of water moisture. During these two periods, diffusion of moisture effectively ceased and no distortion of the PMC was measured.

Based on outgassing tests on duplicate samples held in storage during the lifetime of LDEF, it was found that the dimensional change (measured using a laser interferometer system [4]) as a function of time in vacuum behaved according to Fick's law [4] (see Figure 12); i.e.,

$$M(t)_{T=const} \equiv M_o \exp \left[-7.3 \left(\frac{Dt}{h^2} \right)^{0.75} \right] \quad (2)$$

where M = moisture content, D = diffusion coefficient, h = thickness, t = time. For constant temperature, Shen and Springer [5] have shown that the diffusion coefficient can be calculated knowing the moisture content at different times from the relation,

$$D_{T=const} = \frac{\pi h^2}{16M_o^2} \left[\frac{M_2 - M_1}{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1}} \right]^2 \quad (3)$$

where M_1, M_2 = moisture contents at times t_1 and t_2 , respectively.

Rather than measure moisture content during a test, one can employ strain data (ϵ). Noting that

$$\epsilon = M\beta \quad (4)$$

where β = coefficient of moisture expansion (CME), then Eqs. (2) and (3) can be re-written as,

$$\epsilon(t)_{T=const} \equiv \epsilon_o \exp \left[-7.3 \left(\frac{D_t}{h^2} \right)^{0.75} \right] \quad (5)$$

and

$$D(t)_{T=const} = \frac{\pi h^2}{16\epsilon_o^2} \left[\frac{\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1}{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1}} \right]^2 \quad (6)$$

To develop a model for predicting outgassing of materials in space, it is necessary to take temperature into account. However, Fick's law as previously described applies to constant temperature, constant humidity environments. In space, the humidity level (i.e., vacuum) is constant. Furthermore it is possible to determine a diffusion coefficient as a function of temperature [$D(T)$] by performing outgassing tests at different temperatures (T_a and T_b) assuming an Arrhenius relation between D and T . This yields the equation,

$$D(T) = \exp \left[\frac{\ln(D_b) - \ln(D_a)}{1 - \frac{T_a}{T_b}} + \ln(D_a) \right] \cdot \exp \left[\frac{(\ln(D_b) - \ln(D_a))}{\left(\frac{1}{T_a} - \frac{1}{T_b} \right) \cdot T} \right] \quad (7)$$

This equation can be used to calculate the diffusion coefficient at any temperature, as long as the diffusion coefficients D_a and D_b at temperatures T_a and T_b are known. All of the above temperatures must be absolute (K). Hence, knowing $D(T)$, the strain associated with outgassing $\epsilon(T, t)$ can be calculated from Eq. (5).

Similar tests to that shown in Figure 12 were conducted at different temperatures and the slopes of the $\epsilon(T, t)$ curves used to calculate $D(T_a)$ and $D(T_b)$ [4]. Based on these results, a comparison of the strain change with time for the LDEF specimen was made (see Figure 13). It was assumed in the model analysis that the moisture diffusion process essentially ceases when the temperature dropped to freezing or below (i.e., $D = 0$ when $T \leq 32^\circ\text{F}$ or $\leq 273\text{K}$). It is evident that a reasonable correlation with space flight data can be achieved using the model described. Such an approach is essential to estimate the dimensional change likely to occur in space, particularly when one is designing for 'low distortion' applications.

DESIGN EXAMPLE

To demonstrate how this diffusion data and analysis can be used in the design of low distortion laminates, consider the case of a $(\pm\theta)_s$ structure. The question being addressed is how much axial distortion can occur in a zero coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) laminate due to vacuum outgassing?

Figure 14 presents the variation in the α_x and α_y CTE values for a $(\pm\theta)_s$ laminate fabricated from 5208/T300 material. The case of $\alpha_x = 0$ occurs when $\theta \equiv \pm 46^\circ$. Using diffusion data to calculate the CME values of β_x and β_y from standard laminate analysis, one can obtain from Figure 15 $\beta_x \approx 200 \times 10^{-6}/\% M$ at $\theta = 46^\circ$.

Figure 9

Figure 10. Thermal/strain response of LDEF specimen (3T6), graphite/epoxy 90°, 5208/T300.

Figure 11. A plot of Δ strain versus time in orbit for LDEF specimen (3T6).

Figure 12. Outgassing of sample 5T5 at 50 C. Material: T300/5208, 90° PMC.

Figure 13. LDEF versus ground-based model. Sample 5T5-T300/5208 90°.

Figure 14. CTE for angle-ply laminates. T300/5208 graphite/epoxy.

Assuming a 1% moisture uptake prior to launch yields an axial displacement of $\Delta L = 200 \times 10^{-6} L$ where L = length of structure. Thus for a 10 m long structure, the axial contraction would be 2.0 mm for a zero CTE laminate.

ATOMIC OXYGEN EROSION

Atomic oxygen flux (ϕ) incident on a spacecraft in the ram direction can be calculated as a function of orbital altitude from the relation

Figure 15. CME for angle-ply laminates. T300/5208 graphite/epoxy.

$$\phi = NV \text{ (atoms/cm}^2\text{/s)} \quad (8)$$

where N = number density (atoms/cm³) (see Figure 5), and V = velocity (cm/s). However, corrections should be considered due to orbital inclination and atmospheric motion as well as the random Maxwellian thermal motion of the oxygen atoms which correspond to about 0.49 and 0.41 km/s, respectively [6, 7]. In addition, one must take into account the angular position away from the ram direction to correct for incident flux as well. As a first approximation one can modify the incident flux using the equation

$$\phi = NV \cos \theta \quad (9)$$

where θ = angle of incidence relative to the velocity vector. Because of the random thermal velocity component it has been shown [6, 7] that AO can impinge on surfaces at $\theta > 90$ deg, and reach about 105 deg.

MATERIAL EROSION YIELD FACTOR

The characteristic used to quantify the susceptibility of a material to erosion by atomic oxygen is the erosion yield (R_e). This parameter is defined as

$$R_e = \frac{\text{Volume of material lost}}{\text{Total number of incident O atoms}} \text{ (cm}^3\text{/atom)} \quad (10)$$

R_e can be calculated using the relation

$$R_e = \frac{\Delta m / \rho}{\phi t A} \quad (11)$$

where Δm = mass loss (g), ρ = material density (g/cm³), ϕ = incident AO flux (atoms/cm²-s), t = exposure time (s), and A = exposed surface area (cm²). Note that the product ϕt yields the total fluence of oxygen atoms.

SPACE FLIGHT DATA

Reaction of AO with a variety of materials was reported by Leger [8] as early as 1982, for STS missions 1-3 and in 1984 for flights 3-8 [see Ref. 9]. However, it should be noted that laboratory test data from plasma asher experiments were available as early as 1965 demonstrating the effect of atomic oxygen on polymers [10]. The most extensive data base available to date has been compiled in Ref. 6.

Perhaps the greatest single source of materials degradation data is emerging from the ongoing analysis of the NASA LDEF experiments. Typical erosion surface morphologies observed on PMC materials are shown in Figures 16, 17 and 18. Figure 16 presents SEM photomicrographs of a graphite/epoxy T300/934 laminate exposed to AO at 22° off the ram direction. A cross-sectional view of the same material at 0° is given in Figure 17. Note the 90 μ erosion depth compared to the unexposed reference surface. A graphic example of the effect of AO angle of incidence on the erosion profile is shown in Figure 18. This cross-sectional SEM illustrates the erosion process at 30°, 65°, 75° and 90°, the latter case exhibiting very little mass loss.

A comprehensive analysis of AO effects on PMC materials on LDEF was undertaken to evaluate the erosion process as a function of AO angle of incidence (θ) and to determine if R_e varied substantially for the different PMC materials. An estimate of the erosion loss (h) for a PMC oriented at an angle θ to the normal incident AO flux (ϕ_n) after an exposure time 't' is given by,

$$h(\theta, t) = R_{e_c} \phi_n t (\cos \theta)^{1+m} + h_r \left(1 - \frac{R_{e_c}}{R_{e_r}} \right) \quad (12)$$

where R_{e_c} , R_{e_r} are the 'normal' erosion yield values for the bulk composite and outer surface resin layer (of thickness h_r), respectively.

A plot of the erosion depth $h(\theta)$ is presented in Figure 19 for six PMC materials flown on LDEF. Only one material, 934/T300, was common to four locations.

In Figure 20, it can be seen that a $\cos^{1.5}\theta$ function fits the 934/T300 erosion data rather well, except in the range of $\theta = 82^\circ$. Since half of the erosion depth at $\theta = 82^\circ$ was accounted for by an outer epoxy layer, one would indeed expect erosion to be higher than that for the bulk graphite/epoxy material. Using a value of $m = 0.2$ gave better results at $\theta = 82^\circ$. Included in Figure 20 is a correction factor for the effect of a 10 μ epoxy layer (as measured from the UTIAS samples located at $\theta = 82^\circ$).

Figure 16. Erosion of graphite/epoxy T300/934 material at 22°

Figure 17. SEM micrograph cross-section of 934/T300 (0°)4, from ram side showing shielded edge and the effect of AO erosion.

Figure 18. Cross-sectional SEM photographs of erosion profile at different angular positions (α) around graphite/epoxy composite tube.

A plot of the normal erosion yield values based on $m = 0.2$ in Eq. (12) is presented in Figure 21. It is clear that for $0 < \theta \leq 70^\circ$ essentially constant yield values are obtained, independent of angular location θ because of the larger erosion losses that occurred. For these samples, one is

Figure 19. Erosion depth of PMC materials.

Figure 20. Erosion depth of epoxy matrix composite samples — epoxy layer effect.

Figure 21. Normal erosion yield ($Y_n \cos^2$).

essentially measuring a bulk property not significantly affected by the outer epoxy layer. However, for smaller erosion depths, a larger value is obtained, consistent with the effect of the epoxy layer.

EFFECT OF CHEMICAL STRUCTURE ON EROSION

A study was conducted to establish a relationship between the atomic oxygen erosion rate of hydrocarbon-based polymers and their chemical content and structure. Based on a comprehensive analysis of erosion data for a large number of samples exposed to the low Earth orbit (LEO) space environment and to simulated LEO environment conditions in ground-based hyperthermal facilities, an excellent linear correlation exists between the AO erosion rate and a structural parameter γ defined as the ratio of total number of atoms in a repeat monomer unit to the difference between the total carbon content and the total number of intermolecular oxygen in the same repeat unit (Figure 22). The structural parameter γ actually represents the chemical content of the material, or the relative content of "effective carbon atoms." It would appear that the removal of these "effective carbon atoms" by oxidation is the limiting step for erosion by fast atomic oxygen. Figure 23 provides examples of three polymer materials and the calculation of γ .

PROTECTIVE COATINGS

One method of protecting PMC's from AO erosion is to coat the surface with a passivating layer. Figure 24 shows SEM photomicrographs depicting the efficacy of one such coating, SiO₂. The PMC sample, AS4 3501-6, was flown on STS-46 and received a total AO fluence of $\sim 2 \times 10^{20}$ a/cm². No measurable erosion or mass loss was observed. The cross-section views show clearly the presence of the coating on the outer resin surface. However, it is interesting to note that where a defect in the coating existed, local erosion of the exposed epoxy was visible.

DESIGN NOMOGRAM

Based on the known flux of AO as a function of altitude, it was possible to construct an engineering nomogram showing the thickness loss one could expect for a given material erosion yield based on the total time in orbit and the fluence. This nomogram is presented in Figure 25, with a graphite/epoxy example highlighted. The example parameters selected were:

- altitude = 465 km
- time in orbit = 10⁴ days (= 27.4 years)
- erosion yield = 2×10^{-24} cm³/a

Following the curves as shown, one finds a thickness loss of $\sim 600 \mu$, corresponding to about 5 plies of material.

Figure 22. Effect of polymer structure on erosion yield in presence of hyperthermal atomic oxygen (2-5 eV).

Figure 23. Examples of polymer structures and calculations of $N_T/(N_C - N_O)$.

Figure 24. Graphite/epoxy (AS43501-6) coated with SiO_2 exposed to atomic oxygen for 42 hours. Mission STS-46, July 1992. Fluence = 2×10^{20} atoms/cm².

Figure 25. Erosion of graphite/epoxy at 465 km after 27.4 years in ram direction.

Figure 26. Impact damage on front/back faces of graphite/epoxy laminate.

MICROMETEOROID/DEBRIS IMPACT DAMAGE

The effect of hypervelocity microparticle impacts on PMC's can be seen in the SEM photomicrographs of Figures 26, 27 and 28. A complete penetration with enhanced rear face spallation damage is shown in Figure 26 for a graphite/epoxy laminate. Much less damage appears to be the case for a similar impact on the graphite/PEEK laminate shown in Figure 27. Although there was front and rear face damage, it is not clear just how much interior fracture has occurred until one examines the cross-section in Figure 28.

Figure 27. Impact damage on front/back faces of graphite/peek laminate.

Based on an extensive ground-based test program involving both types of PMC's, a plot of the 'crater area' versus particle impact energy has been compiled in Figure 29. Data taken from one other source has also been included for comparison purposes. It is quite evident that an excellent correlation exists between these two parameters which can be used to estimate the damage on a PMC for a given particle impact energy.

DESIGN NOMOGRAM

From the measured impacts around LDEF after 5.75 years in orbit, a circumferential distribution plot was compiled in Figure 30. Using this data, it was possible to construct a nomogram by simple linear extrapolation of the number of expected hits one would encounter as a function of angle off ram, exposed area and time in orbit. This nomogram is shown in Figure 31 with an example highlighted, corresponding to a ram facing panel of 10 m² area, exposed for 5.75 years. This yields a total of 3100 impacts.

DESIGN CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

- (1) One of the major design advantages of using PMC's is that they can be configured to yield a low distortion structure over a wide temperature range. The challenge is to be able to account for changes in CTE after prolonged exposure in the thermal-vacuum environment, including mass loss due to AO erosion of surface plies. Moisture desorption leading to further dimensional changes must also be considered.
- (2) Protection of PMC's from AO erosion will certainly enhance their utilization on spacecraft. At this point in time, no polymer matrix materials have been developed, suitable for use as a PMC, that are AO resistant. Although coatings such as SiO₂ are very effective, they add additional cost and complexity to the manufacturing of PMC space structures. Opportunities exist to develop low-cost polymer surface modification treatments that will provide the same protection as SiO₂ coatings. Eliminating a coating interface will also enhance operational lifetime by eliminating possible cracking due to thermal cycling.
- (3) In LEO, one of the most serious design challenges is that of fracture, spallation and interior delamination due to hypervelocity particle impacts. Although damage models exist for metallics, no such model supported by test data is available for PMC's.

Back (x100)

Cross-Section (x100)

Figure 28. Impact damage on back face and through the cross-section of graphite/PEEK laminate.

(4) One other area that deserves an initial study is to determine if any synergistic effects arise due to radiation damage and AO. The author is unaware of any PMC investigations in this area. Possible applications exist where higher inclination orbits can lead to increased radiation exposure.

Figure 29.

Figure 30. Circumferential distribution of micrometeoroid/debris impacts on LDEF (NASA M&D/SIG Report, Aug. 1990).

Figure 31

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